

European responses to the COVID-19 worldwide crisis: Did we act too late?

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Running title: European responses to the COVID-19 worldwide crisis: Did we act too late?

Abstract: This Perspective summarizes the different strategies implemented in 46 countries to flatten the epidemic curve of COVID-19. It compares public health responses from Europe with the other countries and it underlines the lack of a common response in Europe. This reflexion raises the question of the right timing of taking social distancing actions and learning from Asian countries.

Main text:

Nearly 3 billion people around the world are under lockdown. 91% of the world's students have schools temporarily closed. Numerous countries have imposed travel restrictions, non-essential place closures, bans on large gatherings, and shelter-in-place orders.

By April 27, the USA reports the highest cumulated incidence with 965,910 confirmed cases, followed by Western European countries (837,917 cases for Spain, Italy, the UK, France and Germany together), Turkey (110,130 cases) and Iran (90,481 cases) [1].

Different implemented strategies

Only China and South Korea have succeeded in slowing this epidemic as of April 1, and notably they leveraged different policy approaches. China took rapid and stringent measures, including a lockdown of Wuhan just 3 weeks after the first unknown pneumonia report to WHO [2]. Other countries followed Chinese sample and imposed people's movements restrictions with different levels of intensity from advice to stay at home in Japan and South Korea, limitations in gathering for 50 people in Sweden, 10 people in Singapore or 2 people in Germany, partial curfew in Guatemala and Chili to a total restriction of movement in several countries such as India, Malaysia, France and South America. In contrast, South Korea did not implement a lockdown but preferred to aggressively deploy testing and efforts to trace contacts of those who tested positive [3]. Although Germany, Iceland and Austria have not yet exited their exponential trajectory of cases, they acted early and pursued a similar approach to the one taken in South Korea, and early signs are indicating this is working. These 3 European countries have a high prevalence and a low ratio of deaths to confirmed cases (Case Fatality Ratio CFR of less than 2%) due to the high capacity test. As of April 4, Iceland tested 6% of the population. On the 27th of April, this proportion reached 12% with a rate testing of 120 per 1000 people [4,5].

Europe is having a hard time

Most Western European countries are currently struggling with its testing capacities, due to a shortage of reactants and a lack of preparation, as well as the healthcare capacity and the ability to obtain adequate supplies of personally protective equipment including face masks and hydro-alcoholic gel [6]. This is reflected by a rising CFR ranging from 10% in Spain to 15% in Belgium [1]. Additionally, the lack of a common case definition and the heterogeneity of testing capacities complicate data comparison. For instance, France is only testing severe cases and only counting death from hospitals, making it difficult to completely characterise the true CFR. European countries are following Italy epidemic curve with a short time-lag of 1.5 - 3 weeks [7]. Moreover, due to the strain on healthcare system caused by the influx of SRAS-CoV-2 patients, a surge in deaths is observed for older people and with comorbidities, and for patients with non-SRAS-CoV-2 illnesses in France, Spain, and in Italy [8].

Acting earlier is better

For the first time 30 EU and Schengen countries have reinstated border controls to contain the pandemic. Most of European countries only took strict actions once the continent had become the epicentre of this pandemic [9]. School closures to slow the spread of COVID-19 were in the first measures but the effectiveness remains uncertain [10].

European response appeared delayed and disjointed.

Italy was the first to lockdown, but only after the virus had taken hold in the north of the country (40 days after the 1st confirmed case). Restriction of movement followed in Spain, in Austria and Denmark. France shut down just after its local election in mid-March which may have helped to spread the virus. The UK government changed approach applying national lockdown only after the number of deaths surged (+1,035 new cases, the day before). Eastern European countries applied similar restrictive measures. Sweden remains an exception with schools, restaurants, and sports clubs still open. Most of countries applied stricter social distancing measures after the WHO's announcement of COVID-19 pandemic (Fig. 1). It is complicated to find a fair and effective middle ground between overly strict and early measures which severely impact economy and society and late actions which leads to catastrophic health consequences for the population.

The delay between the confirmation of the 1st case and national lockdown is between 40 and 56 days for France, Italy, Germany, the UK, Spain when over 1000 new cases per day were registered (Fig 1). In Denmark, Austria, Norway, the Netherlands, Poland and Hungary, strong social distancing measures were implemented sooner (15-23 days) when the incidence was lower (<200 new cases). Countries with a longer delay between the 1st case and national lockdown are now facing a higher incidence of COVID-19. In Europe, only Sweden and Belarus did not set a lockdown. Sweden is experiencing a higher CFR (12%) than the other Scandinavian countries (<5%)

Efficiency of lockdown measures is reflected through the evolution of doubling time of COVID-19 cases: a longer doubling time indicate a slower exponential growth compared to a shorter doubling period. Between the lockdown and 14 days after this measure, doubling time increased by 5-9 days in Saudi Arabia, Latino American countries, Germany, Denmark and Norway whereas it was shorter with 1-3 days in the Western European countries with highest prevalence of COVID-19 [Supplementary Table S1].

Worldwide response

The USA has the highest delay between the first case and the implementation of lockdown measures in some states (58 days after the first case in the USA) [11]. An opposite strategy was adopted by some South American and African countries, and by India which quickly initiated strict lockdown measures.

Hong Kong, Taiwan, Japan, Singapore and South Korea took early measures at the very beginning of this pandemic better managing the spread of the epidemic. For example, Hong Kong began to scan the temperature of travellers by January 3! Hong Kong, Singapore and Taiwan used mobile app to trace back the cases, inform people and follow the spread of SRAS-CoV-2 [12]. All these countries also share the previous experience of SARS-CoV-1 epidemic: having to face a similar situation before, Asian people are probably more prepared to accept the measures needed to stop an epidemic.

High testing capacity, effective isolation of confirmed and suspected cases, quick implementation of specific laws, social distancing, and promotion of sanitary measures are the five key actions to succeed managing an emergent epidemic. Europe will have to learn from this sanitary crisis and should have taken advantage from Asian countries' experience. More European solidarity and coordination will be required to tackle this outbreak.

WHO declarations

Public Health Emergency of International concern

Pandemic

— Delay between 1st case and 1st death
— Delay between 1st case and national lockdown
— Delay between 1st death - National lockdown
— Delay between National lockdown then first death
X (+number of new cases at National Lockdown)

Figure 1:

Title: Timeline describing the delay between the first case, the first death and a national lockdown in 46 countries

Legend: Red line: Delay between the 1st confirmed case and the 1st death

Green line: Delay between the 1st case and a national lockdown

Blue line: Delay between the 1st death and a national lockdown

Purple line: Delay between a national lockdown and the 1st death

X symbol refers to the lockdown event

+number of new daily cases refers to the COVID-19 incidence at the lockdown day

Data retrieved from ECDC database, governmental websites and press articles (Supplementary Table S1)

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Supplementary Material

European responses to the COVID-19 worldwide crisis: Did we act too late?

Supplementary Table S1: Dates of national lockdown and others social distancing measures and its references in 46 countries

Data were retrieved from European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, an agency of the European Union on the 8th of April, 2020 and from UNESCO website for school closure dates: <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>

Country	Continent	Date of first case	Date of first death	Date of National school closure	Type of school closure	Date of national lockdown	Doubling time for cases at lockdown	Delay between the 1st case and lockdown	Delai between the first death and lockdown	Incidence at national containment
Angola	Africa	22/3/20	30/3/20	24/3/20	national	28/3/20	4,5	6	-2	1
Argentina	America	4/3/20	8/3/20	16/3/20	national	20/3/20	3	16	12	31
Australia	Oceania	25/01/2020	1/3/20	24/3/20	local	29/03/2020	5	64	28	431
Austria	Europe	26/2/20	13/3/20	16/3/20	national	16/3/20	3	19	3	205
Belgium	Europe	4/2/20	12/3/20	13/3/20	national	18/3/20	3,5	43	6	158
Bolivia	America	12/3/20	30/3/20	12/3/20	national	22/3/20	3	10	-8	4
Botswana	Africa	1/4/20	2/4/20	20/3/20	national	2/4/20	3,5	1	0	1
Canada (Québec, Ontario)	America	26/1/20	10/3/20	16/3/20	local	25/3/20	2	59	15	Local containment
Colombia	America	7/3/20	22/3/20	16/3/20	national	25/3/20	3	18	3	75
Czech Republic	Europe	2/3/20	22/3/20	11/3/20	national	17/3/20	2,5	15	-5	
Denmark	Europe	27/2/20	16/3/20	16/3/20	national	13/3/20	2	15	-3	160
Finland	Europe	30/1/20	22/3/20	18/3/20	national	27/3/20	6	57	5	78
France	Europe	25/1/20	15/2/20	16/3/20	national	17/3/20	4	52	31	1210
Germany	Europe	28/1/20	10/3/20	18/3/20	national	22/3/20	4	54	12	3276
Greece	Europe	27/1/20	12/3/20	11/3/20	national	23/3/20	6	56	11	94
Guatemala	America	15/3/20	16/3/20	16/3/20	national	15/3/20	2	0	-1	1
Hubei	Asia	3/1/20	11/1/20	23/1/20	national	23/1/20	?	20	12	97
Hungary	Europe	5/3/20	16/3/20	16/3/20	national	28/3/20	5	23	12	43
Iceland	Europe	29/2/20	20/3/20	16/3/20	national	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown
India	Asia	30/1/20	13/3/20	20/3/20	national	25/3/20	4	55	12	70
Iran	Middle-East	20/2/20	20/2/20	26/2/20	national	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown
Ireland	Europe	1/3/20	12/3/20	12/3/20	national	28/3/20	4,5	27	16	302
Italy	Europe	30/1/20	23/2/20	4/3/20	national	10/3/20	3,5	40	16	1797
Japan	Asia	15/1/20	13/2/20	2/3/20	national	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown
Jordan	Middle-East	3/3/20	29/3/20	15/3/20	national	21/3/20	3,5	18	-8	13
Kenya	Africa	14/3/20	27/3/20	16/3/20	national	23/3/20	2	9	-4	8
Laos	Asia	2/3/20		19/3/20	national	30/3/20	5	28		0
Lithuania	Europe	28/2/20	21/3/20	16/3/20	national	14/3/20	2	15	-7	
Malta	Europe	7/3/20	9/4/20	13/3/20	national	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown	No lockdown
Malaysia	Asia	25/1/20	18/3/20	18/3/20	national	18/3/20	3,5	53	0	120
Mexico	America	29/2/20	21/3/20	23/3/20	national	30/3/20	4	30	9	145
Morocco	Africa	3/3/20	12/3/20	16/3/20	national	21/3/20	3,5	18	9	23
Netherlands	Europe	28/2/20	7/3/20	16/3/20	national	16/3/20	3	17	9	176
New Zealand	Oceania	28/2/20	29/3/20	24/3/20	national	25/3/20	2	26	-4	47
Nigeria	Africa	28/2/20	24/3/20	26/3/20	national	30/3/20	4	31	6	0
Norway	Europe	27/2/20	13/3/20	12/3/20	national	13/3/20	2	15	0	132

Pérou	America	7/3/20	20/3/20	16/3/20	national	16/3/20	1	9	-4	28
Poland	Europe	4/3/20	13/3/20	16/3/20	national	24/3/20	4	20	11	115
Portugal	Europe	3/3/20	18/3/20	16/3/20	national	2/4/20	6	30	15	
Romania	Europe	27/2/20	23/3/20	11/3/20	national	24/3/20	2,5	26	1	143
Russia	Europe	1/2/20	27/3/20	11/3/20	national	28/3/20	3	56	1	196
El Salvador	America	19/3/20	1/4/20	11/3/20	national	21/3/20	2	2	-11	2
Chile (Santiago)	America	4/3/20	23/3/20	16/3/20	national	26/3/20	4	22	3	220
Saudi Arabia	Middle-East	3/3/20	25/3/20	9/3/20	national	25/3/20	08/04/2020	22	0	205
Singapore	Asia	24/1/20	22/3/20	No school closure	not closed	3/4/20	10	70	12	49
South Africa	Africa	6/3/20	27/3/20	18/3/20	national	26/3/20	3	20	-1	152
Republic of Korea	Asia	20/1/20	21/2/20	2/3/20	national	No lockdown				
Spain	Europe	1/2/20	5/3/20	11/3/20	national	14/3/20	2,5	42	9	1227
Sweden	Europe	1/2/20	12/3/20	18/3/20	national	No lockdown				
Taiwan	Asia	21/1/20	17/2/20	No school closure	not closed	No lockdown				
Tunisia	Africa	3/3/20	21/3/20	16/3/20	national	20/3/20	4	17	-1	10
Uganda	Africa	22/3/20	2/4/20	20/3/20	national	30/3/20	4	8	-3	3
United Kingdom	Europe	31/1/20	6/3/20	20/3/20	national	23/3/20	3,5	52	17	665
United States of America	America	21/1/20	1/3/20	28/2/20	local	19/3/20	2	58	18	2988
Venezuela	America	15/3/20	27/3/20	16/3/20	national	17/3/20	2	2	-10	18
Vietnam	Asia	24/1/20		28/2/20	local	1/4/20	10			0
Zimbabwe	Africa	21/3/20	24/3/20	24/3/20	national	30/3/20	4	9	6	0

eTable 2: References for the date of lockdown in worldwide countries

All the website were consulted on April 10th, 2020

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Russia	The Russian Government. Meeting of the Presidium of the Government Coordination Council to control the incidence of novel coronavirus infection in the Russian Federation http://government.ru/en/news/39290/
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Malta	Official COVID-19 INFO PAGE for Malta https://covid19malta.info/
Poland	The Chancellery of the Prime Minister. Prime minister: in the battle against the coronavirus we must reduce our mobility to an absolute minimum https://www.premier.gov.pl/en/news/news/prime-minister-in-the-battle-against-the-coronavirus-we-must-reduce-our-mobility-to-an.html The Chancellery of the Prime Minister. Prime Minister: We have decided to close all educational institutions and universities https://www.premier.gov.pl/en/news/news/prime-minister-we-have-decided-to-close-all-educational-institutions-and-universities.html
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South Africa	South African Government News Agency. President Ramaphosa announces a nationwide lockdown (March 23, 2020) https://www.sanews.gov.za/south-africa/president-ramaphosa-announces-nationwide-lockdown
Tunisia	France24. Tunisia orders lockdown due to coronavirus, postpones loan repayments for poor (March 20, 2020) https://www.france24.com/en/20200320-tunisia-orders-general-lockdown-in-bid-to-contain-coronavirus
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Bolivia	Jeanine Añez Chavez Twitter account https://twitter.com/JeanineAnez/status/1241417482239344647?s=20 BoliviaSegura.gob.bo https://boliviasegura.gob.bo/
Venezuela	Gobierno Bolivariano de Venezuela. Presidente Maduro llama a la union nacional para radicalizar la cuarentena social y colectiva http://vicepresidencia.gob.ve/presidente-maduro-llama-a-la-union-nacional-para-radicalizar-la-cuarentena-social-y-colectiva/ Bloomberg. Venezuela Orders Lock-Down as Coronavirus Cases Nearly Double (17/03/2020) https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2020-03-17/venezuela-orders-lock-down-as-coronavirus-cases-nearly-double
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Argentina	Argentina Unida. Argentina governmental website https://www.argentina.gob.ar/noticias/el-presidente-alberto-fernandez-evalua-una-cuarentena-total-0
Guatemala	Reuters. Guatemala extends curfew to avoid spread of coronavirus https://www.reuters.com/article/health-coronavirus-guatemala-curfew/guatemala-extends-curfew-to-avoid-spread-of-coronavirus-idUSE1N29Q00Y The New York Times. Panama Imposes Full-Day Curfew, Guatemala Extends State of Emergency https://www.nytimes.com/reuters/2020/03/24/world/americas/24reuters-health-coronavirus-panama.html
Panama	https://www.presidencia.gob.pa/Noticias/Presidente-Cortizo-Cohen-reitera-llamado-a-la-solidaridad-entre-los-panamenos-y-anuncia-cuarentena-total
USA	Official California State Government Website https://covid19.ca.gov/img/Executive-Order-N-33-20.pdf https://www.gov.ca.gov/2020/03/19/governor-gavin-newsom-issues-stay-at-home-order/?mod=article_inline https://www.flgov.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/EO-20-68.pdf?mod=article_inline https://governor.hawaii.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/2003162-ATG_Third-Supplementary-Proclamation-for-COVID-19-signed.pdf?mod=article_inline A Guide to State Coronavirus Lockdowns https://www.wsj.com/articles/a-state-by-state-guide-to-coronavirus-lockdowns-11584749351
Canada	https://www.canada.ca/fr/sante-publique/services/maladies/maladie-coronavirus-covid-19.html
Hubei Other Chinese administrative divisions	The Guardian. First Covid-19 case happened in November, China government records show – report (13 th March) https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/13/first-covid-19-case-happened-in-november-china-government-records-show-report
South Korea	The Korean Ministry of Education website https://www.moe.go.kr/boardCnts/view.do?boardID=294&boardSeq=79822&lev=0&searchType=null&statusYN=W&page=1&s=moe&m=020402&opType=N
Singapore	https://www.moh.gov.sg/news-highlights/details/additional-precautionary-measures-to-prevent-further-importation-and-spread-of-covid-19-cases Singapore. Ministry of Health. Promulgation of Regulations Under Infectious Diseases Act (26 th March, 2020) https://www.moh.gov.sg/news-highlights/details/promulgation-of-regulations-under-infectious-diseases-act
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Malaysia	MyGovernment. The Government of Malaysia's Official gateway https://www.malaysia.gov.my/portal/content/30936
Italy	Ministero dell'interno. Direttiva ai prefetti per l'attuazione dei controlli nelle "aree a contenimento rafforzato"

	https://www.interno.gov.it/it/sala-stampa/comunicati-stampa/direttiva-prefetti-lattuazione-dei-controlli-nelle-aree-contenimento-rafforzato
France	Gouvernement Français. Informations Coronavirus. https://www.gouvernement.fr/info-coronavirus
Spain	https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2020-3946 Real Decreto 463/2020, de 14 de marzo, por el que se declara el estado de alarma para la gestión de la situación de crisis sanitaria ocasionada por el COVID-19
Belgium	Centre de crise. Covid-19: Restez chez vous, prenez soin de vous et des autres (17/03/2020) https://centredecrise.be/fr/news/gestion-de-crise/covid-19-restez-chez-vous-prenez-soin-de-vous-et-des-autres Belgian Federal Government. Coronavirus: reinforced measures https://www.belgium.be/en/news/2020/coronavirus_reinforced_measures
UK	UK Government. PM address to the nation on coronavirus: 23 March 2020 https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/pm-address-to-the-nation-on-coronavirus-23-march-2020 https://www.gov.uk/government/news/schools-colleges-and-early-years-settings-to-close
Greece	Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis' address to the Greek people https://primeminister.gr/en/2020/03/22/23619 https://primeminister.gr/en/2020/03/17/23599
Finland	Finish Government. Government, in cooperation with the President of the Republic, declares a state of emergency in Finland over coronavirus outbreak https://valtioneuvosto.fi/en/artikkeli/-/asset_publisher/10616/hallitus-totesi-suomen-olevan-poikkeusoloissa-koronavirustilanteen-vuoksi
The Netherlands	Government of the Netherland. The approach to tackling coronavirus in the Netherlands https://www.government.nl/topics/coronavirus-covid-19/tackling-new-coronavirus-in-the-netherlands
Sweden	Regeringen stoppar stora möten https://www.svt.se/nyheter/snabbkollen/regeringen-stoppar-stora-moten https://www.krisinformation.se/nyheter/2020/mars/ytterligare-begransning-sammankomster
Austria	Bundesministerium für Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10000249 Austrian Government http://www.allentsteig.gv.at/Aktuelle_Infos_zum_Coronavirus Coronavirus (COVID-19): Status quo – Schulen, Hochschulen, Universitäten und Forschungsinstitutionen https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Ministerium/Informationspflicht/corona/corona_status.htmlv
Denmark	Statsministeren: Der bliver brug for, at vi hjælper hinanden https://www.regeringen.dk/nyheder/2020/pressemedde-11-marts-i-spejlsalen/
Norway	The Norwegian Directorate of Health https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/nyheter/helsedirektoratet-stenger-alle-barnehager-og-skoler The Norwegian Directorate of Health https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/nyheter/the-norwegian-directorate-of-health-has-issued-a-decision-to-close-schools-and-other-educational-institutions
Portugal	Portugal official website for COVID-19 https://covid19estamoson.gov.pt/#
Germany	Bundeskanzlerin Merkel begibt sich in häusliche Quarantäne. Sonntag, 22. März 2020 https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/themen/coronavirus/bundeskanzlerin-merkel-begibt-sich-in-haesusliche-quarantaene-1733282
Jordan	US Embassy in Jordan. Covid-19 Information https://jo.usembassy.gov/covid-19-information/
Iran	https://www.tehrantimes.com/news/446106/WHO-says-iran-s-strategies-to-control-COVID-19-in-the-right
Saudi Arabia	Ministry of Interior: Curfew in Jeddah Governorate to be effective from 3:00 p.m. on Sunday, and suspension of entry into and exit from it https://www.spa.gov.sa/viewfullstory.php?lang=en&newsid=2052560
New Zealand	Ministry of Health https://www.health.govt.nz/news-media/news-items/covid-19-media-update-25-march https://covid19.govt.nz/

WHO main steps

Date	Main steps
31 December 2019	First case of an unknown pneumonia in Wuhan reported to the WHO
13 January 2020	First case outside of China in Thailand
30 January 2020	WHO declared Public Health Emergency of International Concern
11 February 2020	New name
17 February 2020	WHO issues guidance on mass gathering and taking care of ill travellers
25 February 2020	WHO-China joint mission shares findings and recommendations
2 March 2020	Mission of WHO experts arrive in Iran
3 March 2020	Shortage of personal protective equipment endangering health workers worldwide
7 March 2020	100 000 cases threshold
11 March 2020	WHO characterizes COVID-19 as a pandemic
13 March 2020	Launch of SOLIDARITY Trial Europe becomes epicentre of the epidemic